

Thermal Cycling of W-Wire Reinforced Metal Matrix Composites

R. Warren¹⁾, L. O. K. Larsson²⁾, P. Ekström¹⁾, T. Jansson¹⁾

1) Department of Engineering Metals, Chalmers University of Technology, S-412 96 Göteborg, Sweden
2) Material Laboratory Department 358, Volvo Flygmotor AB, S 461 81 Trollhättan, Sweden

ABSTRACT

A study was made of the thermal cycling of composites of W-wires in matrices of stainless steel, Kovar, Inconel 718 and Hastelloy X. Samples were subjected to up to 3600 cycles between 90 and 925°C. Apart from the Kovar matrix composites all exhibited considerable plastic deformation and grain boundary cracking in the matrix on the sample surface within about 50 cycles. During the first 100 to 400 cycles the wires became fully debonded and began to be pushed out of the composite during further cycling. The debonding was caused by the growth of cracks between the matrix and a thin reaction layer, formed at the wire/matrix interface during fabrication. The initiation and growth of such cracks can be attributed to the high shear stresses generated at the edges of composites.

INTRODUCTION

Composites of W-wire reinforced high-temperature alloys have considerable potential as materials for use at temperatures above those normally possible for the corresponding unreinforced matrix alloys. Successful methods of fabrication have been developed (1,2) in which the wires largely retain their favourable mechanical properties (2,3,4). The problems of recrystallization and degradation of creep properties that are often observed can be reduced significantly by eliminating Ni from the alloy (4,5,6).

A problem that has yet to be solved is that of damage brought about by thermal cycling. This arises not only as a result of thermal gradients in the material but also as a result of the significant differences in thermal expansion between the tungsten ($5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$). A number of reports indicate the possible extent of damage including plastic deformation of the matrix, fibre-matrix debonding and macroscopic deformation of the composite (7-9). Larsson has made an elastic-plastic analysis of the tri-axial stress state to be expected in such composites (10). This revealed the importance not only of the thermal expansion differences but also the details of the mechanical properties of the matrix. Larsson also considered the presence of a brittle reaction layer between fibre and matrix.

The present work describes an experimental study of the thermal cycling behaviour of W-wire composites with four different matrices (stainless steel,

Kovar, Hastelloy X and Inconel 718). Kovar was chosen because of its unusually low coefficient of thermal expansion ($5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ up to 500°C) while stainless steel has a relatively high value ($16\text{--}20 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$). Hastelloy X and Inconel 718 represent Ni-base superalloys, the former without and the latter with γ' precipitation hardening. In contrast to a similar study by Friedman and Fleck (11), in which the samples were heated by passage of an electric current through them, the samples in the present study were not fixed at their ends. A consequence of this was that fibre-end effects became important. For this reason the results are interpreted in terms of an analysis of the stress state to be expected at fibre ends.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material

Unidirectional composites were prepared using a method based on the cladding of W-wires with closely fitting matrix tubes (1). The wires were W-2 wt% ThO₂ with diameter 0.3 μm . Their mechanical properties have been described in (12). The matrix alloys were supplied as tubes with inner and outer diameters of about 0.4 and 0.6 respectively giving a nominal volume fraction of around 0.3. The composition and strength in the annealed state of the matrix alloys are given in Table 1.

Table 1 - Chemical compositions of matrix alloys (wt.%).

	Fe	Ni	Cr	Co	Mo	Ti	Al	Nb/Ta	0.2 % Y.S. at R.T. (MPa)
S/S 321	rest	10	18	--	-	0.3	-	-	190
Kovar	54	29	--	17	-	-	-	-	290
Inconel 718	20	52	18	--	3	1	0.6	5	650
Hastelloy X	18	50	21	2	9	-	-	-	590

Bundles of between 32 and 34 parallel clad wires were packed into outer container tubes of stainless steel or a Ni-Cr alloy. These were sealed and hot isostatically pressed (HIP) at $1050^\circ\text{C}/200 \text{ MPa}/2 \text{ h}$ (Kovar and 321 matrices) or $1100^\circ\text{C}/240 \text{ MPa}/2 \text{ h}$ (718 and HX matrices). After compaction the resulting cylindrical specimens were machined down to a diameter of 3.4 mm and cut to a length of 25 mm. The composite cores were approximately 3.1 mm in diameter but since they did not lie exactly central it was necessary to choose the somewhat larger sample diameter in order to avoid exposure of the wires at the surface. Consequently the composites were often slightly asymmetric axially as well as having an overall volume fraction lower than nominal (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1.
Cross section through a specimen before cycling (approx. 10 x).

Thermal Cycling

The thermal cycling equipment consisted of a vertical, resistance-heated tube furnace into and from which the sample was repeatedly lowered and withdrawn as follows: The sample was sealed into an evacuated silica capsule. The capsule was hung at the end of a silica tube which served as a push/pull rod as well as the cladding of a thermocouple. The tube and capsule were lowered into the furnace by means of an electric motor, activated when the thermocouple registered the pre-set, minimum temperature of the cycle. Similarly, the tube was withdrawn automatically at the pre-set maximum temperature. The furnace was held at a temperature around 50-100°C above the intended maximum cycle-temperature. Cycling was carried out between 90° and 925°C; a temperature vs. time cycle being shown in Fig. 2. Samples were removed for examination after given numbers of cycles between 25 and 3600.

Figure 2.
Showing a single thermal cycle.

Sample Examination

After cycling the samples were examined for macroscopic changes such as distortion and changes in dimensions. Then the surfaces and other relevant features were examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) after which metallographic sections were prepared perpendicular and parallel to the fibre direction. The polished sections were examined optically and in SEM.

RESULTS

Uncycled Specimens

All the composites showed no significant external changes for up to 1000 cycles whereas very marked effects were observed in the other three composite systems. After just a few cycles the originally bright machined surface of the sample took on a matte appearance except for a region of about 1 mm at each end (Fig. 3). With increasing cycles the effect became more obvious and small increases (up to 1-2 %) in length were observed. A slight permanent bending of some samples occurred (Fig. 3) presumably due to the lack of symmetry of the reinforcement.

External Effects of Cycling

Kovar composites showed no significant external changes for up to 1000 cycles whereas very marked effects were observed in the other three composite systems. After just a few cycles the originally bright machined surface of the sample took on a matte appearance except for a region of about 1 mm at each end (Fig. 3). With increasing cycles the effect became more obvious and small increases (up to 1-2 %) in length were observed. A slight permanent bending of some samples occurred (Fig. 3) presumably due to the lack of symmetry of the reinforcement.

SEM examination showed that the change in the sample surface was due to plastic deformation. This is shown in the series of micrographs, Figs. 4a-c. The regular machined surface becomes distorted due to the development of slip bands and marked grain-boundary sliding. After only 50 cycles, cracks and cavities appeared at the grain boundaries. Fig. 5 shows the similar deformation

Figure 3. Typical appearance of a specimen after 50-100 cycles.

Figure 4.
Surface of a composite with an
Inconel 718 matrix

- a) as-machined
- b) 25 cycles
- c) 120 cycles

Figure 5.
End surface of a composite with
an Inconel 718 matrix.

occurring in the ends of samples. Not unexpectedly, deformation is greatest close to the fibres.

An even more dramatic effect of cycling in these three composites was that the wires began to creep out of the composite. Strangely, the wire movement seemed to be predominantly in one direction and so with increasing cycles the wires were pushed long distances out of the composite (Fig. 6). The process began after about 250 cycles in the stainless steel and 718 composites and after 400 cycles in the HX composites. Obviously, this process implies that the wires had debonded from the matrix. Longitudinal sections showed that this occurred by the

Figure 6.
Inconel 718 matrix compo-
site cycled 890 times.

Figure 7. Crack growing at the inter-
face between reaction layer and matrix
(321-matrix composite, 20 cycles)
(SEM on polished section).

Figure 8. Growth of fibre debonding
cracks with thermal cycling (718
matrix). Scatter bands indicate
differences from fibre to fibre.

growth of cracks between the intermetallic reaction layer and the matrix (Fig. 7). This was confirmed by SEM examination of the ejected wires which showed that the layer covered the wire surface. The cracks began at the wire ends and progressed with each cycle towards the centre (Fig. 8). The rate of crack extension in a given sample varied considerably from wire to wire as is indicated by the scatter in Fig. 8. It is also seen in Fig. 8 that the fastest cracks reached the centre of the specimen (i.e. giving complete bonding) after about 100 cycles.

Although Kovar matrix composites showed no external signs of damage, metallographic sections revealed that some cracking occurred in the boundaries between the previous tube surfaces.

DISCUSSION

The most significant effects of thermal cycling revealed by this study are heavy plastic deformation of the matrix and wire/matrix debonding. The deformation is considerable even after a few cycles and would probably lead to rapid composite failure in cases where fibre debonding does not lead to stress relief. The observations confirm the analysis of Larsson (10). This predicts that the matrices examined here should attain their yield stresses during both the heating and cooling regions of the cycle and that they should fail in fatigue after about 1000 cycles.

Wire debonding is undoubtedly associated with the stress state at wire ends. Here the tensile thermal stresses can be assumed to fall to zero while the shear stress at the wire/matrix will increase correspondingly. If the shear stress is sufficient, a crack will form at the interface at the end of the wire. The region of high shear stress will move inwards with the crack and the crack will continue growth with each new cycle. Evidence of an end effect is given by the end zones on the sample surfaces unaffected by plastic deformation (Fig. 3). Such edge effects arising from thermal stresses have been reviewed by Yaniv and Ishai for laminate composites (14). The case of fibre composites of the type studied here are treated below.

The differences in the strengths and the thermal expansion of the three matrices (321, 718 and HX) did not give measurable differences in the plastic deformation. However, the HX composites survived a greater number of cycles before complete debonding occurred. This may indicate the benefit of its somewhat lower yield strength (compared to 718) and lower expansion coefficient (relative to stainless steel). Kovar matrix composites resist thermal cycling damage. This indicates that the majority of damage in the other matrices occurs below about 500°C since above this temperature Kovar has a similar thermal expansion to these.

Shear stresses at wire ends

The above results emphasise the importance of the conditions at the wire ends. In the previous stress analysis of thermal fatigue properties of composite materials, by Larsson (10), all end effects were neglected. In the present study the conditions close to the wire ends were analysed by a general finite element program (FEM) for stress analysis. The program used was ANSYS and isoparametric solid 3-D elements were selected for the analysis. Both elastic and elastoplastic solutions were sought.

Results obtained so far indicate that very high shear stresses are generated at the wire/matrix interface close to the wire ends. Figure 9 shows an example of the shear stresses estimated with an elastic calculation for a W-wire/Stainless Steel Composite subjected to thermal cycling between 20°C and 925°C. This not only shows that the level of the shear stresses is locally high but also indicate the length of the effected region, this corresponding well with experiments.

Figure 9
 Calculated max shear stresses in the matrix at wire/matrix interface in a W/SS321 composite. z is the distance from the wire end and r is radius from the wire center

The combination of extremely high shear stresses and a relatively weak wire/matrix interface due to the presence of brittle phases are sufficient to explain the observed debonding with crack initiation at the wire ends. The shear stress concentration can be expected to move together with the crack propagation along the wire/matrix interface.

Only marginal problems with debonding were reported by Friedman and Fleck (11) for composites similar to those here. This can be explained by the fact that Friedman and Fleck used cooled grips and specimen ends while in our tests the full specimen length was cycled. Comparison of the two experiments demonstrates the importance of composite ends. A proper material combination and very good bond between wire and matrix could improve the composite thermal fatigue resistance. A design criterion to reduce thermal fatigue problems could be to avoid subjecting the composite ends to thermal cycling.

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